

Influence Of Organisational Climate On Employees' Productivity Among Staff Of Selected Hospitals Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

In health sectors and specifically hospitals, it is very important for hospitals to stay focused on their employee performance and seek ways to enhance it. While employees are assets in any organization, the importance of an employee in hospital settings is more significant because the industry is by nature manpower intensive. Most of the employee activity and behaviour in the hospitals involves direct contact with patients. Performance is a major multi-dimensional construct aimed at achieving results. Hence, this study investigates the role of organizational climate on employees' productivity.

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. It adopted a stratified random sampling technique was used to select the participants from the population of the study. This technique was employed because the population of the study was broken into strata considering the department they worked and level. With each stratum a representative of the population of the study where participants were selected from Adeoyo State Hospital and University College Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State. The use of questionnaire was adopted for data gathering from Two hundred and Twenty participants.

The result showed that there was a positive significant relationship between job performance and autonomy in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .264$, $N = 220$, $p < .05$). Hence, autonomy had a positive influence on job performance in the study, there was also that there was a positive significant relationship between job performance and team work in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .715$, $N = 220$, $p < .05$). Furthermore, there was a positive significant relationship between job performance and reward and recognition in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .537$, $N = 220$, $p < .05$), was a positive significant relationship between Job Performance and fairness in selected hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .555$, $N = 220$, $p < .05$). However, there was there was a negative significant relationship between Job performance and reward system in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = -.144$, $N = 220$, $p < .05$).

In conclusion, the study finding indicated that organizational climate dimensions which were discussed in this study (Support, Fairness, Trust, Autonomy, Reward and Recognition and cohesion of team workers) have positive relationship with employee's job performance and the variables understudy contributed about that 55.7% of the variance that was accounted for by the predictor variables when taken together.

Keywords: Organisational climate, employees' productivity, job performance

Word counts: 386

Introduction

In the twenty-first century, organisations face greater difficulties than ever before. These issues impact all organisations, regardless of size or structure, and are not exclusive to any one sector or organisation. Changes affecting organisations today present ongoing challenges, particularly to organisational climate. Organisational climate, according to Schneider (2023), is the result of a social information process that involves the meaning that workers ascribe to the rules, processes, and practices they encounter as well as the behaviours they see being rewarded, encouraged, and anticipated (Nair, 2016). Organisations typically have several concurrent climates rather than just one. It is crucial to continuously and firmly encourage a healthy work environment that is employee-focused in order to meet the organization's process and employee productivity goals.

Organisations needed the contributions of high-performing individuals (workers) to supply the goods and services they were specialised in in order to effectively accomplish organisational goals and gain a competitive edge (Sonnentag & Frese, 2022). However, low work attitudes (Suleiman, 2023), inefficiency (Obasanjo, 2003), and deteriorating standards for the supply of public goods and services in terms of both quantity and quality (Salisu, 2021) are characteristics of public sector employees' productivity in developing nations like Nigeria. Due to public uproar over these issues, the government implemented a number of public sector reform initiatives, including those from 1997 to 2007 and 2010 to 2013.

With the goal of increasing employee productivity for optimal service delivery and boosting their efficiency and effectiveness, these reforms rationalise ministries and departments, review public service organisational structures, and introduce SERVICOM, an agency created to guarantee that citizens enjoyed efficient and effective goods and service delivery. However, as recently emphasised by Inyang and Akaegbu (2024), the development of an efficient, capable, and high-performing workforce in the public sector depends heavily on the design and implementation of effective human resource management (HRM) strategies and practices. In every organisation, workers are seen as a valuable resource for high and efficient employee production.

According to Armstrong (2009), both the work environment and the people inside the organisation contribute to increased employee productivity. Currently, one of the most important factors for employees to produce high-quality work is the work environment. Employees' intentions to work are influenced by a nice and healthy work environment. Lewin (1951) is typically credited with creating the notion of organisational environment through his field theory of motivation. For many years, industrial/organizational psychologists have considered the idea of corporate or work atmosphere to be one of the most crucial elements to consider (Sunstag 2003, quoted Guion).

In organisations that mediate the link between objective aspects of the work environment and people's responses, climate perceptions are seen as crucial determinants of human behaviour (Campbell, Dunnette, Lawler, & Weick, 1970). An employee's opinion on their workplace has been defined as the organisational climate (Hellriegel & Slocum, 2024).

Schneider and Snyder (1975) assert that the molar or holistic character of climate perceptions is such that they serve as a framework for achieving a certain level of congruence between behaviour and the practices and procedures of the system.

Additionally, Thompson (2025) cited Schneider, who conducted research on workplace productivity. Schneider's findings indicate that organisational climate is a significant determinant of employee productivity, and that employee productivity is equal to climate and ability, emphasising the display of individual differences. How workers view and understand their work surroundings is referred to as the organisational climate (James & Jones, 2024). The more empirically obtainable components of organisational climate are behavioural and attitudinal traits.

Climate, according to Moran and Volkwein (1992), is a relatively persistent feature of an organisation that sets it apart from others. It represents members' collective opinions about their organisation in relation to aspects like autonomy, trust, cohesiveness, support, recognition, innovation, and fairness; it is created through member interaction; it provides a foundation for situation interpretation; it reflects the prevailing norms and attitudes of the organization's culture; and it acts as a source of influence for behaviour shaping. Giving employees autonomy inside a company will also increase their productivity. The ability to utilise authority freely and fearlessly is referred to as autonomy. It entails allowing the worker to benefit from the authority of their position while staying within the parameters established by the company.

The management encourages employees to take responsibility and respects their feelings. The more responsibility a person has, the more autonomy they have. Employee confidence and mutual respect between employers and employees are the results of autonomy. Good delegation may increase employee productivity and foster a culture of appropriate autonomy inside the company (Choudhury, 2011). According to Newman (2010), autonomy is also the capacity of the worker to choose how and how they do their duties. As it aids in meeting each employee's internal psychological demands, it is a significant intrinsic motivation and ought to have a favourable correlation with dedication. Dewhurst (2010) asserts that the incentive structure implemented by the company has a major impact on workers' productivity. Employee rewards can be given in ways other than monetary pay, though. Among them are the recognition that staff members receive from their supervisors, the chance to work on significant projects or assignments, and even the chance to receive leadership attention. The latter is the practice of managers treating staff members in a way that makes them feel like leaders even themselves. These three motivators are consistently found in the majority of research studies and are great ways to motivate people to put in more effort and achieve higher levels of productivity.

The main reason for this is that the employee who receives a high incentive thinks that the firm they work for values them. Knowing that their employers care about their well-being and that their company is fostering and supporting their professional and personal growth also motivates them to perform harder and better. Therefore, it is an ongoing and ongoing challenge for organisations to truly concentrate on understanding what elements lead to increased employee productivity.

In addition to focussing on customer or patient satisfaction, it is important for businesses to discover the factors that increase employee productivity so that they may provide their staff with enough and suitable offerings. Employee productivity inside the company may also be influenced by workgroup cohesiveness. "A cooperative process that enables ordinary people to achieve extraordinary results" is the definition of teamwork. In order to accomplish shared objectives, a team's members might build productive, reciprocal connections. Teamwork is the result of people cooperating in a cooperative setting to share knowledge and abilities in order to accomplish shared team goals (Harris & Harris 1996).

Therefore, for a team to be successful, there must be synergy among all members of the team, fostering an atmosphere where everyone is eager to engage and contribute in order to foster a productive, positive team environment. Team members need to be adaptable enough to function in collaborative settings where social interdependence and teamwork are used to accomplish goals rather than solo, competing ones. Steers (2007) found a favourable correlation between employee productivity and sentiments of commitment and social contact chances. Coworker satisfaction is viewed as a measure of how much employees appreciate their working connections with one another, which is anticipated to have a positive correlation with commitment and increase employee productivity. Hence this study will be guided by the following objectives which includes to:

- i. Evaluate the influence of cohesion of team worker on job productivity of employees of workers in hospital
- ii. Examine the impact of rewards on job productivity of employees of workers in hospital
- iii. Determine the impact of recognition on job productivity of employees of workers in hospital
- iv. Examine the influence of fairness on job productivity of employees of workers in hospital
- v. Investigate the influence of autonomy on job productivity of employees of workers in hospital.

Literature Review

Cohesion and Employees productivity

In particular, Beal, Cohen, Burke, and McLendon (2003) carried out a meta-analysis of the connection between employee productivity in organisational groups and group cohesiveness. Their analysis's primary goals were to: 1) re-evaluate the criteria used in group cohesion studies; 2) retest the relationship between group cohesion and employee productivity using refined criterion categories; 3) reevaluate the independent contributions of the following variables in group cohesion studies: task commitment, interpersonal attraction, and group pride; and 4) look into the effect of work flow patterns on the relationship between group cohesion and employee productivity (Beal et al., 2003). Employee productivity may be seen as both a behaviour and an outcome, according to Beal et al. (2003), while the majority of academics concentrate on employee productivity as an outcome domain. Beal et al. (2003) assert that employee productivity is based on their actions rather than their outcomes.

The group cohesion (social and task), employee productivity (behavioural and productivity of employees), team type (production, service, project), and team setting (academic and organisational) aspects of the relationship between group cohesion and job productivity of employees were all examined in a recent meta-analysis by Chiochio and Essiembre (2019). The authors proposed that project teams in organisational contexts are different from other teams and noted that prior meta-analytic researchers have not examined project teams.

The following were among the theories put out by Chiochio and Essiembre (2009): 1) Compared to production or service teams, project teams will have more positive correlations with employee productivity and task cohesion; 2) project teams will exhibit larger positive correlations between task cohesion and employee productivity, followed by social cohesion and employee productivity, task cohesion and employee behaviour, and finally social cohesion and employee behaviour; 3) project teams will show stronger positive correlations between cohesion and employee productivity than service or production teams. Additionally, the researchers examined the two opposing theories listed below: According to Chiochio and Essiembre (2009), 4a) organisational project teams exhibit higher positive social cohesion correlations than workers project teams, and 4b) workers project teams also show higher positive social cohesion correlations than organisational project teams.

Reward System and Employee Productivity

According to research by Ali and Ahmad (2009), "recognition and reward" and "employee productivity" are positively correlated. They claimed that employee productivity would significantly increase if they received rewards and recognition. The purpose of the study was to examine the connection between staff productivity and incentives in

Pakistani schools. These factors include the environment, gender discrimination, work description, extrinsic and intrinsic rewards, employee productivity, reconditioning methods, and employee productivity bonuses. They employed cement businesses, collected data via a questionnaire, and randomly delivered 200 surveys to private school personnel in Pakistan's Khyber Pakhtoonkhawa Province. The findings showed that employee productivity and reward systems are directly correlated (Qureshi, Zaman, & Shah, 2010).

Mishra and Dixit (2013) assert that under an education incentives system, employee productivity is strongly connected with both monetary and non-monetary rewards and benefits. Employee job satisfaction also rises as a result of the favourable correlation between incentives and productivity. Feelings of accomplishment and success at work are correlated with job happiness. Employee productivity and effort on the workplace are also associated to increased enjoyment, excitement, and a sense of fulfilment (Kaliski, 2007). In his research, Boehm and Lyubomirsky (2008) examined how rewards increase pleasure and work satisfaction. Employee productivity is determined by both intrinsic and extrinsic rewards (Clifford, 1985).

According to Andrew and Kent (2004), who conducted this study, all employees are focused on incentives and recognition, therefore both are very important to them. Reward systems that are effective in keeping top performers in the company must satisfy their needs (Carragher, Gibson, & Buckley, 2006). According to Csikszentmihalyi (1990) and Flynn (1998), staff morale is raised, employee productivity is linked to employee rewards, and employee spirits are maintained through recognition and reward programs. Establishing a mechanism for payment and informing employees of it so they may relate their reward to their production is the fundamental goal of recognition and reward programs.

In addition to having a favourable correlation with the motivating process, rewards are a key factor in deciding how productive individuals are at work. Lawler (2003) discovered that the amount of a reward and the weight that individual assigns to it are the two criteria that affect how desirable a reward is. According to Deeprose (1994), "Good managers reward people by giving them something tangible and recognise people by doing things that acknowledge their accomplishments." Promotions that are fair and based on an employee's abilities and talents encourage loyalty and serve as a source of relevant workability. According to Bull (2005), when employees achieve success in intellectually hard jobs, rewards and recognition are the important aspects of today's incentive programs, since these tie the success factor with employee productivity.

Fairness and Employee Productivity

Job satisfaction, employee productivity, employee withdrawal behaviours (e.g., absenteeism, turnover), counterproductive work behaviour (e.g., employee theft), organisational commitment, and organisational citizenship behavior are all outcomes associated with organisational justice. Two recent meta-analyses found that distributive justice, procedural justice, and other forms of interactional justice were all linked to many of the outcomes listed above (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt, 2001). Associations followed the expected pattern: high levels of organisational justice predict good work satisfaction, high staff productivity, low disengagement, less counterproductive behaviours, strong organisational commitment, and more organisational citizenship activities. These data suggest that exposure to organisational injustice is linked with outcomes comparable to those caused by occupational stress.

Employee productivity (e.g., Beehr, Jex, Stacy, & Murray, 2000), job satisfaction (e.g., de Jonge, Bosma, Peter, & Siegrist, 2000; Tetrick, Slack, Da Silva, & Sinclair, 2000; Zivnuska, Kiewitz, Hochwarter, & Perrewew, 2002), and withdrawal behaviours (e.g., Bakker, Demerouti, de Boer, & Shoufeli, 2003; Zivnuska et al., 2002) have all been found to be impacted by exposure to varied occupational stressors. These results imply that inadequate organisational justice may have a negative impact on workers' health and well-being and serve as a workplace stressor.

Autonomy and Employee Productivity

Stamps and Piedmonte (1986) describe autonomy as the degree of independence, initiative, and freedom linked to one's employment that is either allowed or necessary in day-to-day work activities. Employee happiness has been positively correlated with autonomy (Parker & Wall, 1998; Hackman & Oldham, 2010; Neuman, Edwards, & Raju, 1989). According to the findings of numerous other studies, employee autonomy is a crucial element of their professional growth (Hart & Rotem, 1995; Manley, 1995; Grey & Pratt, 1989) and increases their job productivity (Blegen, 1993; Weissman, Alexander, & Chase, 1980; Finn, 2001).

Given the unstructured nature of complex jobs that demand judgement, creativity, decision-making, and other discretionary behaviours from employees (Chung-Yan, 2010), Frese and Zapf (1994) contended that people with discretion and control are better able to solve problems because they are free to choose how to handle the circumstance. In general, researchers have identified two forms of job autonomy—task control and time control—

that can have a good impact on individuals' job productivity. Task control may be further broken down into the task's methodology and the daily organisation of work materials to maximise productivity.

Time management has gotten much less attention and, at best, generated conflicting results. This is in contrast to autonomy regarding work method, which refers to the degree of freedom that workers have in going about their work, such as the kind of spreadsheet software an employee prefers to use (Hackman & Oldham, 1976; Sims, Szilagyi, & Keller, 1976). The degree of control employees have over the time, sequencing, and scheduling of their job activities—such as the option to work from home vs report to work—is referred to as autonomy in work scheduling.

In the case of the Netherlands, taking breaks during working hours, choosing the order of tasks, stopping work at any time to take a break, and choosing how to complete tasks all demonstrated positive and statistically significant associations with employees' job productivity, according to the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions report (2006).

Recognition and Employee Productivity

According to Matlala (2011), the organisation might enhance and promote the usage of efficient recognition in the employee management system's feedback process about productivity. According to the findings, a recognition program may also persuade the business to consider a more formal recognition process that would enable the strong culture it aspires to. According to Grawitch et al. (2016), employee productivity is increased by both formal (bonuses, awards) and informal (verbal praise, peer recognition) forms of recognition; however, informal acknowledgement has a more immediate motivating impact. Furthermore, Brun and Dugas (2018) emphasised that regular, prompt acknowledgement works better than occasional awards to maintain high employee productivity.

According to Meyer and Allen (1997), the idea that an individual's sense of value within the company may be greatly impacted by the compensation they receive for their efforts explains the positive effects of rewards like pay and incentives on work attitudes. Saks (2016) asserts that increased rewards and acknowledgement of workers' productivity help to ensure that workers are mentally content and that the job is a good match for them. Employees are willing to respond with their highest degree of dedication to their company when they win awards or recognition from it.

According to Gostick and Elton's (2007) analysis of a study of 200,000 workers, correctly executed employee recognition may boost customer service and profitability while also increasing staff engagement and job productivity.

According to Nelson (2025), acknowledgement promotes better cooperation (employees are more likely to offer assistance and go above and beyond), improved communication (employees are more likely to offer solutions and new ideas), and lower absenteeism and turnover (employees will demonstrate higher job productivity of employees and loyalty). According to Daniels (2019), supervisors may improve employee quality and productivity by simply increasing the frequency of contingent positive reinforcement they provide on a daily basis. Peer and/or management recognition and positive reinforcement are beneficial to employees.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. This was considered appropriate because, it is an empirical method which presents a description of events as they were and the variables were not manipulated. The design also enhanced easy collection of factual information about the influence of organizational climate on employees' job performance in some selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State. The population of the study comprises of workers from selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select the participants from the population of the study. This technique was employed because the population of the study was broken into strata considering the department they worked and level. With each stratum a representative of the population of the study. Two hundred and twenty participants were selected from the population of employees in selected organisations from Ibadan, Oyo State. It was assumed that the selected samples have common characteristics or elements of the population of the study. Based on this, an inference was drawn and generalization was made on the population of the study.

A single instrument tagged "Organizational climate and employee performance Questionnaire (OCEPQ) was used for the study. The job performance scale consists of 25 items measuring the job performance of employees' in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State. The items were drawn from Goodman and Svyantek (1999) job performance scale. The participants were asked to respond to a 4-point rating scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). It yielded a Cronbach alpha value of 0.60. While Organizational climate scale consists

of 32 items measuring organizational climate construct as perceived by employees that works in Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State. It is subdivided into segments such as perceived autonomy with 5 items ($\alpha = 0.74$), cohesion of team workers with 5 items ($\alpha = 0.70$), reward and recognition with 7 items ($\alpha = 0.86$), fairness with 7 items ($\alpha = 0.82$) and reward system ($\alpha = 0.78$). The items were drawn from Duffy, Duffy and Kilbourne (2001), organizational climate Scale. The participants were asked to respond to a 5-point rating scale ranging from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly Disagree (1).

Results

Testing of Hypotheses:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between job performance and employees perceived of autonomy in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Table 1: PPMC showing the relationship between job performance and autonomy in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Job Performance	73.3091	7.7209	220	.264	.000	Sig.
Autonomy	16.0636	3.9106				

Table 1 above showed that there was a positive significant relationship between job performance and autonomy in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .264, N = 220, p < .05$). Hence, autonomy had a positive influence on job performance in the study. The null hypothesis is rejected. The findings of this study corroborates Chen and Chiu, (2009) that autonomy act as a factor to enhance employees motivation to give more effort into their work. It is because employees who are given the autonomy will have more liberty to control and regulate the pace of work and its processes and also be able to evaluate the procedures of work.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between job performance and team work and cohesion in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Table 2: PPMC showing the relationship between job performance and team work in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Job Performance	73.3091	7.7209	220	.715	.000	Sig.
Team Work & Cohesion	24.2091	4.1941				

Table 2 above showed that there was a positive significant relationship between job performance and team work in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .715, N = 220, p < .05$). Hence, team work and cohesion had a positive influence on job performance in the study. The null hypothesis is rejected. Having a team work and cohesion at the place of work of employees will significantly enhance the job performance of workers because working as a team will reduce conflicts that could reduce the productivity and performance of workers while working as a team with cohesion will further enhance the creativity level of each of the team member and this will further enhance the job performance of the organization.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between job performance and reward and recognition in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Table 3: PPMC showing the relationship between job performance and reward and recognition in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
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Job Performance	73.3091	7.7209	220	.537	.000	Sig.
Reward and Recognition	22.9636	6.3848				

Table 3 above showed that there was a positive significant relationship between job performance and reward and recognition in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .537, N = 220, p < .05$). Hence, reward and recognition had a positive influence on Job Performance in the study. The null hypothesis is rejected. When workers observed that they are being recognized at their place of work for the job done as well as compensation with reward it will further enhance the performance of employees especially when employee attach importance to external reward more that intrinsic.

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between job performance and fairness in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Table 4: PPMC showing the relationship between job performance and fairness in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Job Performance	73.3091	7.7209	220	.555	.000	Sig.
Fairness	26.3091	6.7597				

Table 4 above showed that there was a positive significant relationship between Job Performance and fairness in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = .555, N = 220, p < .05$). Hence, Fairness had a positive influence on Job Performance in the study. The null hypothesis is rejected. It can be observed that employees always want fairness in justice, equity in treatment of employees at the hospital settings.

Ho5: There is no significant relationship between job performance and reward system in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Table 5: PPMC showing the relationship between job performance and reward System in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Job Performance	73.3091	7.7209	220	-.144	.032	Sig.
Reward System	14.7727	6.2966				

Table 5 above showed that there was a negative significant relationship between Job performance and reward system in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State ($r = -.144, N = 220, p < .05$). Hence, reward system had a negative influence on job performance in the study. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Ho6: There is no joint effect of autonomy, team work, reward and recognition, fairness, reward system on job performance in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Table 6: ANOVA showing the joint effect of autonomy, team work, reward and recognition, fairness, reward system on job performance

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
.747	.557	547	5.1960			
A N O V A						
Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Regression	7277.249	5	1455.450	53.908	.000	Sig.
Residual	5777.733	214	26.999			
Total	13054.982	219				

Table 6 above showed that the joint effect of Autonomy, Team Work, Reward and Recognition, Fairness, Reward System on Job Performance in selected Organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State was significant. The table also showed a coefficient of multiple correlation of $R = .747$ and a multiple R^2 of .557. This means that 55.7% of the variance was accounted for by the predictor variables when taken together. The significance of the composite contribution was

tested at $<.05$. The table also showed that the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the regression yielded an F-ratio of 53.908. This implies that the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable was significant and that other variables not included in this model may have accounted for the remaining variance. This implies that all the variables of interest considered in this study have a potent contribution to job performance of employees. This corroborates the finding of Saks, (2006) that when the employees received recognitions or rewards from their organization; experienced fairness in treatment, autonomy to a large extent and team work/cohesion; they would be willingness to react through their best level of job performance towards their organization. It also corroborates the findings of Fauziah (2010) that all variable of organizational climate have a significant relationship with job performance of employees.

Table 7: Relative contribution of autonomy, team work, reward and recognition, fairness, reward system on job performance in selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Stand. Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta Contribution		
(Constant)	42.726	2.571		16.621	.000
Autonomy	-9.427E-02	.109	-.048	-.861	.390
Team work	1.004	.108	.545	9.282	.000
Reward and recognition	.143	.094	.118	1.514	.132
Fairness	.220	.083	.192	2.635	.009
Reward system	-8.478E-02	.058	-.069	-1.454	.147

Table 7 revealed the relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable: that autonomy ($\beta = -.048, p>.05$) had no significant relative contribution, team work ($\beta = .5458, p<.05$) had significant relative contribution, reward and recognition autonomy ($\beta = .118, p>.05$) had no significant relative contribution, Fairness ($\beta = .192, p<.05$) had significant relative contribution and Reward ($\beta = -.069, p>.05$) had no significant relative contribution on job performance among workers in some selected organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State. The findings from this study reveals that relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable: that Autonomy ($\beta = -.048, p>.05$) had no significant relative contribution to job performance of employees. This negates the findings of Marchese and Ryan (2001) that autonomy on jobs contributes to a higher level of liability and responsibility for behaviour and conduct, that leads towards improving employees performance and commitment, high motivation and self-confidence, Team Work ($\beta = .5458, p<.05$) had significant relative contribution to job performance of employees. This is in line with the findings of Collins and Parker (2010) that teams develop collective beliefs regarding their capability in a variety of ways, and the collective beliefs lead to team potency and job performance. Reward and Recognition ($\beta = .118, p>.05$) had no significant relative contribution to job performance this negates the findings of Ali and Ahmad, (2009) that there is positive relationship between “recognition and reward”, “performance”. They stated that if reward and recognition are given to employee then there is a huge change in employee performance.

Furthermore the result showed that Fairness ($\beta = .192, p<.05$) had significant relative contribution to job performance. This corroborates the findings of (Garriga, 2012; Zablah 2005; Van Burg et al. 2013) that fairness perceptions can also encourage the participation in inter-organizational and open innovation that would further enhance the job performance of employees and Reward ($\beta = -.069, p>.05$) had no significant relative contribution.

Conclusion

Based on previous theories and researches regarding organizational climate and its outcomes, this study shows the links between organizational climate and job performance, which helps to deeply understand the relationship between the two variables. This finding also support the view points that positive Organizational climate can enhance the positive perception of the employees toward their organization and then increase their job performance in the organization. Based on the study finding, it can be conclude that there was strong positive relationship between organizational climate and employees’ job performance. This implies that when employees have high positive perceptions their organizational climate, they are more likely to perform better in their job role in the organization. On the other hand, negative perceptions of organizational climate are likely to cause employees to withdraw and uncommitted in their organization.

The study finding indicated that organizational climate dimensions which were discussed in this study (Support, Fairness, Trust, Autonomy, Reward and Recognition and cohesion of team workers) have positive relationship with employee’s job performance and the variables understudy contributed about that 55.7% of the variance that was

accounted for by the predictor variables when taken together. Furthermore, it was revealed that autonomy had no significant relative contribution, team work had significant relative contribution, reward and recognition autonomy had no significant relative contribution, fairness had significant relative contribution and reward had no significant relative contribution to job performance of employees in organisations in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Recommendations

- i. Organisational managements should give room for some level of autonomy to the workers so as to enhance the creativity level as well as ability to come up with decision that could contribute to the goal of the organization.
- ii. Managers or supervisors should always treat the employees with respect; politeness and dignity in the workplace to enable them have a sense of belonging and therefore contribute up to their maximum fullest.
- iii. Employees should be made to feel that they are treated impartially by their organisation in every aspect. Decision makers must always give special attention to issues like safeguarding workers, allocating monetary resources, policy-making in respect of justice as they affect employees in the organisation. This will make employees show more positive attitude and behaviour towards their work.
- iv. Employers should give room for cohesion among workers as this can further aid job performance and reduce the conflict that could escalate among groups.

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